

UKRI National Compute Ecosystem Town Hall Meeting Report

Date: 2 June 2026

Location: Riverside Room, County Hall, Belvedere Road, London, SE1 7PB

The National Compute Ecosystem Town Hall Meeting was organised and led by the UKRI Infrastructure team. There were 100 delegates from around the UK with a range of research backgrounds (see Annex 1 for the list of participants). This meeting report provides a high-level summary of the discussions from the town hall meeting.

Please note that this report is a synthesis of the event discussions and does not constitute a statement of UKRI policy or policy intent. The insights gathered will, however, inform UKRI's approach in this area.

The meeting involved updates from UKRI and DSIT on the vision of the National Compute Ecosystem and delivery of the UK Compute Roadmap.

There were three facilitated sessions on:

- Vision and implementation of the Next National Supercomputing Service
- Accessing National Compute Resources
- Looking ahead: exploring innovative practices for the future of digital research infrastructure (DRI)

Introduction

The [UK Compute Roadmap](#) (July 2025) sets out the vision for a world-class compute ecosystem that provides a platform for innovation, growth and opportunity across the economy. This includes the investment of up to £750 million for a new national supercomputer service in Edinburgh. The Next National Supercomputing Service (NNSS) will provide a compute infrastructure for the UK's research and innovation communities to utilise cutting-edge modelling, simulation and AI workflows. UKRI has also recently announced a £76 million investment to launch four new National Compute Resources (NCRs) as part of building a world-class compute ecosystem.

The town hall meeting aimed to engage the research and innovation community in UKRI's plans for NNSS and the NCRs. Note, the AI Research Resource was not in scope.

The interactive event provided an opportunity to:

- discuss the vision and implementation of the NNSS, including its contribution to national research and innovation Grand Challenges and associated access routes, software and user support.
- discuss the approach to creating Community Centres of Excellence as a new consortia-based mechanism for accessing NCRs and supporting the development of research and innovation platforms.
- identify and explore innovative practices for the future of digital research infrastructure.

The presentation slides from the town hall meeting can be accessed via this page:

<https://zenodo.org/records/20539798>

Facilitated session 1: Vision and implementation of the NNSS

In this session, the delegates discussed three key themes:

1. Grand challenges
2. Access routes
3. Software and user support

Theme 1: Grand challenges

1. *What characteristics make a challenge suitable to be considered a compelling and impactful Grand Challenge on NNSS?*

Summary of the discussion

- A compelling and impactful Grand Challenge should align strongly with IS8+, government priorities, and UKRI missions, supported by clearer definitions and granularity from UKRI.
- It must deliver meaningful societal, economic, environmental, and scientific impact, and represent an ambitious step change beyond current capabilities by generating new knowledge, methods, and innovation.
- Grand Challenges should be grounded in well-defined research and innovation questions, rather than being driven solely by infrastructure or technical capability.
- They may involve complex, system-of-systems problems and require cross-disciplinary integration.
- A clear structure and progression are essential, with achievable milestones that build towards more ambitious outcomes. Proposals should carefully balance ambition with deliverability, taking into account practical constraints such as software readiness, supply chains, and policy considerations.
- Successful Grand Challenges will require coordinated expertise, infrastructure, and tools, including appropriate use of CPU/GPU resources and advanced workflows.

2. *What makes a Grand Challenge consortium credible and fair?*

Summary of the discussion

- A credible and fair Grand Challenge consortium should be inclusive, supporting emerging communities by providing clear entry pathways and ensuring that areas with lower HPC maturity are not excluded. It should be driven by scientific questions and merit, rather than by technical capabilities or software maturity.
- Governance should be transparent, with clearly defined roles, responsibilities, and leadership across consortia, Centres of Excellence, and allocation bodies. Allocation processes must be open and fair, with published outcomes, and research leadership should be separated from resource allocation decisions to avoid conflicts of interest.
- Collaboration should be actively encouraged across communities, using shared tools and approaches to connect researchers and align efforts. Existing software, infrastructure, and community expertise should be reused wherever possible to avoid duplication.
- Consortia should be time-limited but flexible, allowing for evolution over time, including the development of sub-challenges and phased approaches.
- Decision-making should be supported by expert panels with sufficient continuity and a long-term perspective.

- Strong user support should be provided, including training and clear progression pathways for researchers, particularly early-career users.
 - Consortia should foster international collaboration and alignment with global infrastructures, alongside shared policies and federated access models.
3. *Please share any thoughts you have on the potential examples of Grand Challenges that were presented.*

Summary of the discussion

- Some examples were seen as too focused on infrastructure, lacking a full research and innovation framing.
- The Grand Challenges should integrate scientific questions, software and methods development, international collaboration, pathways to impact and benefit realisation.
- There is a need to balance short-term outcome-driven challenges with longer-term method development.
- It is important to consider whether consortia roles extend beyond compute to delivering impact.

Theme 2: Access routes

1. *What could simple and fair access look like in practice? What examples or experiences (positive or negative) can we learn from?*

Summary of the discussion

- Simple and fair access should build on proven community-led models, including delegated allocation structures, while also ensuring alternative routes are available for communities less suited to this approach.
- Transparent processes are essential, including the publication of allocation outcomes, clear definitions of access routes, and open decision-making supported by domain expertise in both science and computing.
- Flexible, tiered access pathways should be introduced to support a wide range of users, including fast-track routes for new or pilot projects, discretionary time for testing and onboarding, and small-scale allocations to maximise system utilisation. These stepping stone approaches, such as pilot or scaling phases, should be available from the outset and provide clear progression routes towards larger-scale use, including Grand Challenges.
- Access models should ensure strong coordination across the ecosystem, including alignment with Communities Centres of Excellence and shared service layers that support innovation, data access, and workflows.
- Communities will require appropriate technical expertise, including research software engineering support, to assess readiness and scaling requirements.
- Consortia-based approaches can be effective, provided they maintain openness, avoid duplication of access routes, and support sharing of good practice across projects.
- Dynamic and adaptive allocation mechanisms, such as periodic reviews, pilot runs, and flexible scheduling (e.g. dedicated large-scale run periods), can help ensure responsiveness to evolving needs.
- Clear pipelines, milestones, and prioritisation processes for Grand Challenges should be established.

2. *With risk vs reward in mind, how do we distribute access to NNSS to strike the right balance between enabling ambitious projects and staying realistic about what can deliver measurable impact?*

Summary of the discussion

- There is a need for a balanced portfolio of projects, spanning short- and long-term timescales, as well as low- and high-risk activities, to maximise both impact and learning. This should include ambitious flagship projects alongside smaller or lower-risk studies, ensuring a diverse set of outcomes aligned with strategic priorities such as IS8+.
- A mix of access routes will be required to support the balance of projects, including pilot and scaling stages that enable the development and testing of more ambitious initiatives.
- Cascaded or “funnel” models, where projects progress through stages and are down-selected over time, would be a practical way to manage risk while enabling ambition.
- Multidisciplinary approaches may offer opportunities to address high-impact challenges with relatively lower risk, although they may require additional support for community-building and collaboration.
- It is important to consider reassessing the role of track record in allocation decisions as potential over-reliance on established reputations can limit innovation, and mechanisms to mitigate this include reserve lists or alternative entry routes.
- Risk tolerance should be clearly defined by UKRI, including an understanding of acceptable levels of failure. Sharing learning from both successful and unsuccessful projects, along with strong dissemination of outcomes, will be critical to strengthening the overall ecosystem and improving future access models.

Theme 3: Software and user support

1. *As a user of national compute systems, what support elements do you think are most important for you to enable effective use and impact?*

Summary of the discussion

- Effective user support should begin early, helping users to understand their requirements and identify appropriate services before systems go live.
- Access to testbeds, development environments, and early hardware is critical to enable code development, porting, and scaling preparation.
- Strong support for software porting and optimisation is essential, alongside robust, well-functioning compilers and software stacks.
- Support must reflect the diversity of the user base, ranging from individual researchers to large collaborations, and accommodate varying levels of expertise. This includes enabling “bring your own code/environment” approaches while providing the necessary support to bridge gaps between user applications and system capabilities.
- It is key to have sufficient skilled personnel, including domain-specific research software engineers (RSEs) and system experts, who can provide both long-term continuity and flexible, project-specific support.
- Communities require support to prepare for and transition to new systems, including funding and resources for pre-access development, as well as mechanisms to maintain and evolve legacy software.

- Data support should be integrated alongside compute, recognising the growing importance of large-scale data workflows and roles such as data stewards.

2. What user support tends to work best at a national level, and what works better locally?

Summary of the discussion

- National-level services are well suited to providing core infrastructure support, consistent software environments, shared tools, and coordination across systems.
- Local or community-based support is often better placed to deliver discipline-specific expertise, user engagement, and hands-on assistance.
- Empowering communities with appropriate funding and resources to provide local support is critical, alongside clear definitions of roles across national services, Centres of Excellence, and community-led initiatives.
- Local “champions” can play a valuable role in signposting users to appropriate support mechanisms.
- Flexibility is important to allow support to be delivered by those best positioned to do so, including domain experts and external engineers who can build additional layers of services and tools.

3. What does “excellent user experience” look like?

Summary of the discussion

- There should be clarity, consistency, and ease of use. This includes clear, accessible documentation, straightforward onboarding processes, and transparent access and governance models.
- The systems should enable a smooth transition between different services, with joined-up workflows and minimal barriers to entry.
- Users should have reliable access to testing and development resources, including seedcorn or pilot allocations and interactive or fast-turnaround queues, to support rapid iteration and onboarding.
- Dynamic and responsive support models, such as helpdesk systems with dedicated teams, are essential to resolve issues efficiently.
- The systems should be fit for purpose, with software and workflows that run effectively on the platforms, and with sufficient flexibility to meet the needs of different communities.
- Building long-term relationships between users and support teams, and ensuring continuity of expertise, are key to enabling sustained impact.
- There should be sharing of good practice, learning from international examples, and support for collaboration across communities.

Facilitated session 2: Accessing NCRs

In this session, the delegates discussed the set of questions listed below but were asked to answer them based on an assigned persona on the table. The types of personas were:

- Early career researcher
- Experienced user of national compute systems
- Industry user (including large/medium companies and SMEs)

- New discipline entrant
- Consortia/network community leader

The questions were:

Based on the access models (Community Centres of Excellence (CCEs), grants, and rapid access/seedcorn) described in the presentation, through the lens of the assigned persona on your table:

1. What would make access feel fair and transparent?
2. Where might be the risks of exclusion or unintended barriers to access?
3. How should new or emerging communities be supported?
4. What does good vs excellent support look like?

Early career researcher

Summary of the discussion:

- **Fair and transparent access:** Eligibility should be clearly communicated so all potential applicants understand they can apply. Processes should use consistent, accessible language and provide clear guidance on the “rules of the game.” Assessment should be robust and credible, for example through a single cross-domain panel with appropriate expertise, combined with regular turnover to balance continuity and fresh perspectives.
- **Risks of exclusion and unintended barriers to access:** Over-reliance on track record and grant-writing experience can disadvantage ECRs and those outside established pathways. Complex application requirements, particularly combining scientific and technical cases, can create barriers. Additional risks include limited recognition of outputs such as software, lack of feedback to unsuccessful applicants, and structural challenges such as career instability, institutional dependence, and career breaks.
- **Supporting new and emerging communities:** Support should include proportionate, light-touch application processes and dedicated access routes that provide a clear progression towards larger opportunities. Eligibility must be clearly communicated, supported by targeted calls and proactive outreach. Mentorship and advocacy from CCEs, experienced researchers, and institutional networks are essential, alongside community-building activities and early-stage access to build capability and confidence.
- **Defining good and excellent support:** Good support should combine accessible documentation, training, and clear links between allocation and capability-building opportunities. Flexible training models (including self-directed learning) and community forums can help users develop skills and share best practice. Excellent support provides tailored pathways for different user groups, including dedicated routes and mentoring for ECRs, and fostering inclusive and supportive environments. This includes rapid and flexible access options (e.g. pilot or test access), reassurance for less experienced users, and recognition of diverse career stages and needs. It should also enable continuity of support across transitions, encourage collaboration and knowledge sharing between communities, and ensure that users feel confident, valued, and able to fully engage with the system.

Experienced user of national compute systems

Summary of the discussion:

- **Fair and transparent access:** This requires clear governance and strong coordination across CCEs to ensure consistent and equitable support. Transparency should be embedded throughout, including publishing allocation outcomes, clearly communicating processes, and making panel structures and decisions visible. Models such as EuroHPC highlight the value of a single access route, cross-disciplinary assessment panels, and robust technical evaluation. Greater visibility of data, such as system usage, efficiency, and allocations, through accessible portals can further strengthen trust and accountability. Allocation models should also balance stability and flexibility, offering long-term commitments for large-scale and international projects (e.g. through pooled or pledged allocations) alongside adaptable durations and timing to reflect the needs of different types of research and experimental schedules.
- **Risks of exclusion and unintended barriers to access:** Barriers include limited transparency, inconsistent access routes, and weak coordination across the ecosystem. Discontinuity of access is a key risk, particularly for long-term projects, international collaborations, PhD students, and fixed-term staff. Over-reliance on informal, experience-based support can also disadvantage new users and create uneven institutional burdens.
- **Supporting new and emerging communities:** New users require structured entry points supported by coordinated national, community, and institutional provision, rather than reliance on peer networks alone. CCEs have a key role in representing user needs beyond compute, providing mentorship, and ensuring broad disciplinary coverage. Effective support should include dedicated onboarding, capability building, and mechanisms that reduce dependence on local expertise.
- **Defining good and excellent support:** Good support includes clear documentation, transparent processes, and accessible user support structures, alongside accountability mechanisms to ensure that allocated resources are used effectively. Systems should provide appropriate support for different experience levels, ensuring that new users are guided while experienced users can work efficiently. Excellent support goes further by integrating coordinated, well-resourced support across community, institutional, and national levels, ensuring that no group is disadvantaged. It includes proactive user support, continuity of expertise, and systems that enable users to focus on research rather than navigating complexity. Excellent support creates a balanced environment where both new and experienced users are empowered, expectations are clear, and the system operates efficiently and equitably.

Industry user (including large/medium companies and SMEs)

Summary of the discussion:

- **Fair and transparent access:** Access should be governed by clear rules, consistent expectations, and equitable allocation processes across all user groups. This includes transparent peer review, clear justification for use of limited public resources, and defined funding models (e.g. paid access or collaboration). Eligibility, access routes, and engagement mechanisms must be clearly communicated for all organisations, including SMEs, large companies, charities, and public bodies. Standardised terms and template agreements can improve consistency and reduce barriers.
- **Risks of exclusion and unintended barriers:** There are challenges around software licensing (particularly where academic-only licences apply), data restrictions (e.g. non-commercial datasets or confidential industry data), and intellectual property ownership. Trusted Research Environments (TREs) and security requirements may also create

additional legal and operational complexity, particularly if not proportionate to user needs. Further risks include unclear expectations around access (e.g. whether industry must pay, collaborate, or meet specific criteria), potential conflicts of interest, and differing requirements for data segregation within projects. Smaller organisations such as SMEs and start-ups may face additional barriers due to limited funding, expertise, and capacity, while overly open models may deter industry participation where IP protection is critical. Wider risks include competition for limited capacity, inequitable allocation between academia and industry, and misalignment with government priorities or ethical considerations.

- **Supporting new and emerging communities, including industry:** Tailored access routes are needed to reflect the differing needs of industry, particularly SMEs and start-ups. Targeted support should include access to RSE expertise, mentorship, and brokerage via CCEs or research organisations. Lessons can be drawn from existing models, such as UKRI Catapults, which successfully bridge academia and industry. Clear user journeys and guidance are essential to help organisations understand how to engage, whether through direct access, collaboration, or mediated routes. Flexible and rapid access mechanisms are particularly important for industry, alongside long-term commitments that enable organisations to integrate HPC into their workflows. Engagement through incubators, partnerships, and existing research networks can further support onboarding and collaboration.
- **Defining good and excellent support:** Good support includes clear guidance on how HPC systems can be used (e.g. as research versus production environments), accessible documentation, and appropriate security and data handling frameworks. Provision of cloud services and flexible infrastructure options can help meet diverse industrial requirements. Excellent support would include offering tailored, responsive engagement, such as dedicated account or business partner models, and support that reflects the differing needs of SMEs, large organisations, and other non-academic users. It includes proportionate approaches to security (e.g. TREs), robust IP and legal frameworks, and integrated support across compute, software, and data. It should ensure a balanced and sustainable model where industry access complements, rather than displaces, academic research, while fostering collaboration and maximising overall impact.

New discipline entrant

Summary of the discussion:

- **Fair and transparent access:** There should be a clear understanding of demand, alongside visible and accessible entry points for all users. Access routes should extend beyond established community structures, ensuring individuals and ECRs can apply independently where appropriate. Clear, easy-to-navigate information, such as an up-to-date catalogue of available resources and their suitability, can help users understand options and make informed decisions. Transparency in roles, particularly around CCEs and other support mechanisms, is essential to reduce confusion and ensure consistent engagement.
- **Risks of exclusion and unintended barriers:** Barriers to access often arise from gaps in support, particularly for new or non-traditional users who may lack the expertise to assess technical requirements or navigate application processes. The absence of clear intermediate steps between small-scale access and larger programmes can leave ECRs and new disciplines without viable entry points. Reliance on informal or volunteer-based community support can also create inconsistencies and limit scalability. Patchy local provision of expertise across institutions can lead to unequal access to support and resources.

- **Supporting new and emerging communities:** Support should provide clear, end-to-end pathways from early experimentation to large-scale access, including simple entry routes (e.g. seedcorn or access to HPC calls) combined with structured guidance. Pilot access should be paired with technical support to help users scope future work. A mix of national, domain-specific, and strengthened local support is needed, alongside mentorship, partnerships with experienced groups, and core allocations for new entrants. Proactive engagement through conferences, networks, and virtual and in-person support will broaden participation and build capability.
- **Defining good and excellent support:** Good support provides users with clear guidance on available opportunities, access processes, and technical requirements, alongside a range of support mechanisms such as documentation, training, and access to experts. It should enable users to ask questions freely and receive timely, practical assistance. Excellent support provides a coordinated, multi-layered system that anticipates user needs and removes barriers. This includes continuous monitoring of new users to identify challenges early, seamless integration of different support types (technical, application, and domain-specific), and strong alignment between national, community, and institutional provision. It also ensures there are no gaps between stages of access, providing a coherent and supportive pathway from first engagement through to advanced use.

Consortia/network community leader

Summary of the discussion:

- **Fair and transparent access:** Fairness requires clearly defined CCE remits and access processes, with consistent communication so all users understand eligibility, routes, and expectations. A common framework across CCEs is needed, while allowing flexibility for community-specific needs. Transparency should include visible decision-making (e.g. committee review, community input, published outcomes) and clear allocation rules, durations, and pathways between systems (e.g. NCR to NNSS). Strong coordination or an “umbrella” function is needed to align CCEs, avoid duplication, and share best practice, while maintaining focus and avoiding mission creep. Flexible access options, such as rapid access, discretionary allocations, and longer-term routes, should be combined with clear boundaries and accountability for outputs.
- **Risks of exclusion and unintended barriers:** Barriers arise from gaps between access tiers, particularly for projects too large for NCRs but not suited to NNSS, and from unclear progression pathways. Short allocation periods can limit effectiveness for complex or longer-term projects. Additional risks include ambiguity in CCE purpose, limited flexibility for different workloads (e.g. non-CPU codes), unclear system roles (e.g. day-to-day science versus large-scale challenges), capacity constraints, and weak integration across the ecosystem. Fragmented or overlapping routes, with the potential of “double dipping”, can further complicate access.
- **Supporting new and emerging communities:** Emerging communities require clearly defined entry points and progression pathways, including routes beyond short-term seedcorn access and options for longer-term or more substantial allocations. Dedicated calls for emerging users, potentially with adapted timelines and expectations, can help build capability. Support should include advice at proposal stage (integrating scientific and technical planning), as well as coordination through CCEs, consortia, and community leaders. Mechanisms to identify and grow new communities (such as data-driven

approaches, outreach, and proactive engagement) are essential, alongside support structures that do not rely solely on pre-existing networks.

- **Defining good and excellent support:** Good support provides clear guidance on access routes, durations, and system suitability, alongside responsive mechanisms such as rapid access and discretionary allocations. It should help users navigate the ecosystem and make informed choices about where and how to apply. Excellent support builds on this by offering a coherent, flexible system that adapts to changing user needs, including dynamic allocation models and a balance of short- and long-term access. It ensures continuity where needed, particularly for larger or collaborative projects, and integrates support across applications, allocations, and delivery. Overall, it should enable a seamless user journey across systems, with clear progression pathways and minimal administrative or structural barriers.

Facilitated session 3: Looking ahead: exploring innovative practices for the future of DRI

The DRI landscape is rapidly changing all the time, such as with advances in technology, political and economic drivers, and the rise of agentic approaches (to automating workflows, data management and analysis, and software development and maintenance) etc. This brings a host of challenges and opportunities. We want to build a DRI ecosystem that meets evolving research needs rather than just current demand.

This session focused on looking into the future (5-10 years on), discussing emergent and future requirements for DRI, sharing ideas on opportunities to introduce innovative practices into the ecosystem and ways we could better prepare for the future.

In this session, the delegates were free to discuss any of the five topics below:

- Emerging technologies
- Agentic systems
- Digital sovereignty
- International practices
- Cybersecurity

Emerging technologies

- *What could we do to better prepare ourselves for the integration of emerging technologies, such as quantum and neuromorphic computing, into the wider landscape in the future to start using new technology at the right time?*
- *How might we design federated national compute and research infrastructures that both accelerate emerging technologies and remain openly accessible for broad experimentation and benchmarking?*

Summary of the discussion

- Establish a coordinated national approach to emerging technologies, with CCEs playing a key role in testing new methods and applications and acting as a bridge between technology specialists and research communities.
- Develop testbeds alongside existing infrastructure to enable experimentation, integration with legacy software and data, and early access to new hardware and software environments.

- Ensure strong alignment and collaboration across UKRI initiatives (e.g. with NQCC), while supporting a diverse portfolio of emerging technologies (e.g. quantum, neuromorphic, AI) rather than focusing on a single “winner.”
- Provide open, accessible routes for experimentation and benchmarking, including wider access to testbeds and simulators, so communities can build readiness and explore use cases safely.
- Invest in skills, people, and career pathways (e.g. RSEs/RTPs), ensuring both the development of new expertise and retention of existing capabilities as technologies evolve.
- Enable community-led innovation through pathfinder projects, embedding expertise within research organisations to identify opportunities and accelerate adoption.
- Promote agility in funding, infrastructure, and project design to respond to rapid technological change, including flexible mechanisms to scale investment as technologies mature.
- Build a strong culture of knowledge sharing, continuous learning, and risk tolerance, supported by examples, best practice, and mechanisms for collaboration across communities.
- Integrate industry partnerships and international examples to support innovation, inform procurement, and ensure the UK remains competitive.
- Embed sustainability considerations, data management, and lifecycle planning (including transitioning or retiring models and technologies) as core components of future infrastructure design.

Agentic systems

As agentic systems begin to automate workflows, data, and software development, how could we actively govern their evolution to maximise benefit while managing systemic risk?

Summary of the discussion

- Promote resilience and sovereignty through open-source AI models, strong domestic capability (skills and software), and reduced dependency on large commercial providers, while maintaining the benefits of international collaboration.
- Govern agentic systems through clearly defined, testable proof-of-concept use cases to ensure validity, reproducibility, and safe deployment before scaling.
- Prioritise skills development and retention to maintain the expertise needed to design, operate, and critically evaluate agentic systems, recognising workforce capability as a key competitive advantage.
- Ensure transparency, accountability, and agility in agent behaviour and configuration, with clear information for users and robust mechanisms for monitoring, validation, and risk management.
- Strengthen security, identity management, and governance frameworks to address emerging risks, including cybersecurity vulnerabilities, uncertain costs, and loss of control over autonomous systems.
- Adapt infrastructure to support agentic workflows, including investment in data alongside compute, expanded storage models (e.g. object stores, lakehouses), and stronger national networking capabilities.
- Manage the growing “data deluge” through improved data strategies, including data minimisation, better cataloguing, and integrating storage with compute to enable efficient processing and reduction at source.
- Enable federated and distributed approaches (e.g. federated training across systems) while recognising varying levels of community readiness and capability.

- Foster agility in policy, funding, and infrastructure to respond to rapid technological change, including the ability to scale investment as technologies mature and adapt existing programmes.
- Support innovation through alignment with emerging technologies, while embedding sustainability considerations across system design and operation.

Digital sovereignty

How could the community work with UKRI and DSIT in shaping policy on digital sovereignty and other emerging strategic technologies?

Summary of the discussion

- Develop a clear national strategy, informed by community input, to define where the UK should prioritise sovereign capability and where partnership (e.g. at European level) is more effective.
- Prioritise skills, people, and capability as the foundation of sovereignty, alongside investment in software, models, and expertise rather than infrastructure alone.
- Promote open-source software and models to reduce vendor lock-in while maintaining flexibility to build or adapt systems as needed.
- Address tensions between openness and sovereignty, providing clearer guidance on ownership, access, and risk management, including dependencies on vendors, hardware, and software supply chains.
- Strengthen risk management frameworks, including consideration of geopolitics, export controls, licensing barriers, and long-term sustainability of key technologies (e.g. compilers, languages).
- Encourage international collaboration models where appropriate (e.g. defence or aviation), while maintaining UK self-determination and control over critical assets.
- Consider resilience and the critical dependencies while maintaining the benefits of international collaboration.
- Improve access to software, tools, and codes, addressing licensing constraints that limit participation and innovation.
- Explore investment in domestic hardware and infrastructure, recognising the economic trade-offs and need to coordinate beyond the UK where necessary.
- Support development and hosting of sovereign AI capabilities (e.g. UK-based models and LLM infrastructure), while recognising that data centres alone do not constitute sovereignty.

International practices

What opportunities are there to build on international practices in DRI and how can we implement those practices in the outset?

Summary of the discussion

- Build on proven international models, such as EOSC, ELIXIR, and national initiatives, which demonstrate the value of coordinated, federated infrastructures and strong community integration.
- Prioritise standards, interoperability, and high-quality metadata to enable effective data sharing, reuse, and collaboration across borders and disciplines.

- Develop federated operations and infrastructure, learning from initiatives such as EuroHPC, EESSI, and European federation programmes, to support seamless integration of resources and services.
- Adopt flexible system design, avoiding rigid separation of workloads (e.g. AI vs non-AI) and enabling dynamic use of resources, as seen in facilities such as CSCS and CINECA.
- Encourage open-source software and shared technology stacks to support portability, collaboration, and reduced dependency on specific vendors or regions.
- Strengthen international partnerships and joint funding mechanisms, including coordinated calls and shared investment, while recognising practical constraints such as Brexit-related barriers and travel limitations.
- Ensure a balanced, long-term approach to international programmes, avoiding overly short-term models and enabling sustained collaboration and infrastructure development.
- Promote a “give and take” approach to global collaboration, where the UK both contributes to and benefits from shared capabilities, expertise, and innovation.

Cybersecurity

How might cybersecurity need to evolve as the landscape changes, e.g., if digital identity becomes the most valuable and contested resource in society or systems are too complex for humans to fully understand?

Summary of the discussion

- Formal frameworks, e.g. ISO certification, are not sufficient on their own. Continuous vigilance, monitoring, and adaptive approaches are required too.
- Current reliance on informal or under-resourced vulnerability discovery (e.g. by researchers) is unsustainable; greater funding and support for cybersecurity expertise is needed.
- There is a risk that cybersecurity considerations/requirements could become paralysing.
- Security considerations must be embedded early in the development of AI models and data infrastructures, particularly given growing concerns around data sensitivity and misuse.

Annex 1: List of delegates

The list below only includes delegates who have provided consent for their name and affiliation to be shared.

Adrian Hines	Science and Technology Facilities Council
Alain Zemkoho	University of Southampton
Ali Turner	EPSRC
Andrea Sharpe	NERC
Andrew C Coward	National Oceanography Centre
Anne Trefethen	University of Oxford - Chair of STFC Compute Advisory Board
Anushka Sharma	SPAN
Barbara Montanari	UKRI STFC Scientific Computing
Ben Yarnall	UKRI
Bryan Lawrence	NCAS, University of Reading
Chris Cantwell	Imperial College London
Chris Richardson	University of Cambridge
Christian Oganbule	UKRI
Christina Kerr	Department for Science, Innovation, and Technology (DSIT)
Christopher Maynard	Met Office
Daniela Hensen	BBSRC
David Moxey	King's College London
David Stevens	University of East Anglia
Davide Costanzo	University of Sheffield
Deborah Greaves	University of Oxford
Dr Alex Owen	Queen Mary University of London
Dr Owain Kenway	University College London
Eamonn Bell	Durham University
Ed Bennett	Swansea University
Edward Smith	Brunel University of London
Emily Lumley	Imperial College London
Felix Ruechardt	Department for Science, Innovation, and Technology (DSIT)
Felix Sainsbury-Martinez	University of Leeds
Garth Wells	EPSRC
George Beckett	University of Edinburgh
Hannah Griffin	ISIS Neutron and Muon Source, STFC
Ivo Tews	University of Southampton
Jack Daniel Hollister	Natural History Museum, London
James Earl-Fraser	Jisc
James Gebbie-Rayet	STFC - HECBioSim
James Massey	University of Cambridge
Jiawei Mi	University of Hull
Jon Blower	National Oceanography Centre
Jonathan Bermudez	UKRI

Jonathan Hays	Queen Mary University of London / NFCS / IRIS
Jonathan Yates	CCP for NMR Crystallography / University of Oxford
Karina Rodriguez Echavarria	University of Brighton
Katherine Rooke	STFC
Kay Yeung	UKRI
Kevin Hanley	The University of Edinburgh
Laura Lewis	UKRI
Leah Morabito	Durham University
Louise Chisholm	Advanced Research Computing UCL
Luigi Del Debbio	The University of Edinburgh
Luke Abraham	National Centre for Atmospheric Science and University of Cambridge
Luke Davis	UKRI
Mark Parsons	EPCC, The University of Edinburgh
Mark Storr	AWE NST
Mark Wilkinson	DiRAC HPC Facility / University of Leicester
Mark Woods	Centre for Modelling and Simulation - CFMS
Martin Jones	Francis Crick Institute / CCP-volumeEM
Martin O'Reilly	The Alan Turing Institute
Martin Strawson	UKRI
Michael Bluck	Imperial College
Michal Krepis	University of Warwick
Miguel Bezares	University of Nottingham
Monica D'Onofrio	University of Liverpool
Neha Vaidya	Department for Science, Innovation, and Technology (DSIT)
Neil Sandham	University of Southampton
Nick Brown	EPCC at the University of Edinburgh
Paul Clark	EPCC, The University of Edinburgh
Paul Quinn	STFC
Peter Clapham	Wellcome Sanger Institute
Peter Clarke	University Edinburgh / GridPP
Peter Coveney	University College London
Peter Hill	University of York/Plasma HEC
Phil Hasnip	UKCP HEC/University of York
Pip Jackson	UKRI
Rebecca Scott	NERC, UKRI
Richard Booth	University of Leeds
Richard Gunn	UKRI
Rick Anderson	STFC Hartree Centre
Rod Viggers	UKRI
Roger William Lewis Jones	Lancaster University
Rosalyn Hatcher	NCAS-CMS / University of Reading

Rosie Wood	The Alan Turing Institute
Scott Woodley	UCL, MCC, MMM Hub
Simon Hands	DiRAC / University of Liverpool
Simon McIntosh-Smith	University of Bristol
Sophie Liddell	EPSRC
Sophoclis Patsias	Rolls-Royce
Stephen Longshaw	UKRI STFC
Steven McEachern	UK Data Service, University of Essex
Stewart Clark	Durham University
Sylvain Laizet	Imperial College London
Takis Tsoutsanis	Cranfield University, Faculty of Engineering and Applied Sciences
Tim Snow	Diamond Light Source
Timo Betcke	University College London
Tobias Weinzierl	Durham University
Tony Burdett	BioFAIR, Earlham Institute
Viv Kendon	University of Strathclyde
Wahab Kawafi	University of Bristol
Wendi Liu	STFC-UKRI
Will Roper	University of Sussex